

THE ROLE OF THE STOCK MARKET IN ATTRACTING INVESTORS

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One of the most effective ways to achieve the economic development of countries, the increase in the level of well-being of the population, and at the same time, the manifestation of a competitive and stable developing country on the world scale, is to attract capital of foreign and local investors to the country. The existing stock market in the country and its level of development, efficiency, and transparency indicators are among the important factors, as well as the investment environment created in the country, and its investment attractiveness.

In recent years, investors have realized the role of the stock market in attracting capital investments, and several productions are being carried out to ensure the existing capital market.

Additional publications to the Decree No. PD-6207 [1] of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2021 "On measures for the further development of the capital market" Reform of the securities market in the program "Development of the capital market in 2021-2023", improvement of legislation in this area, protection of investors' market rights, effective regulation of capital and cooperation with financial institutions indicate production. When Western literature talks about the term "investment", the first attention is focused on stock markets and stock exchanges, which indicates that the capital market takes place at the level of production in investments, since market resources include investments, capital, securities. being in the structure, the bulk of the investments will be implemented in this form. V.V. Bocharov, one of the economists of our time, when the word "investment" is mentioned in his scientific works, it means that in the outside world of Europe (USA, Canada, Great Britain, Japan) more attention is paid to the stock markets and such investments made with the help of securities. stated that investments are carried out under the name of portfolio investment [2]. In fact, if we study the structure of the current investment world, we can witness that this idea and vision remains actual even in the 21st century. Financial investments include stocks, bonds, and the like, and are electronic securities or businesses [3]. Investing in securities such as stocks and bonds has several advantages for the investor. The construction of the country's capital market serves to control its

investment attractiveness. Companies in the country take into account the normative ratio between dividends and reinvestment in their dividend policy, protect the rights of small shareholders, achieve an increase in the market price of shares, make profits, etc., which allows the investment attractiveness of the companies, which allows the business to make the country's investment attractiveness [4]. The stock market provides investors with an opportunity to invest in companies whose information is clear, transparent and open, thereby earning capital appreciation and income as the value of their investment increases. Allocating one's own capital to portfolio investments guarantees the investor not only profits from changes in the market price of securities, but also dividends that are presented to him annually or quarterly. In addition, the stock market allows investors to diversify their investment portfolios by investing in a wide range of companies in different industries and sectors. Diversification of capital investments helps the investor to protect his capital from potential risks.

As the stock market is distinguished by its transparency policy and the availability of open information about companies, they serve as a reliable basis for attracting capital from foreign investors. In the current era of globalization, the development of technology and remote and online ways of earning income indicates that investing in the stock market has become more and more easy and open for individual investors. Online brokerage platforms and investment apps have made it easier for investors to buy and sell stocks, manage their portfolios, and access investment research and analysis.

Taking into account the importance of the stock market in the weight of domestic and foreign investments attracted to the country, in order to fundamentally improve the capital market in our country - Uzbekistan, and thereby increase the volume of incoming portfolio investments, "Development of the capital market in 2021 - 2023" program has set several goals and objectives. Establishing investment funds in cooperation with international financial institutions, holding roundtable discussions and seminars on issues of increasing investment attractiveness in the capital market, active integration with international financial markets, extensive use of modern information and communication technologies, and advanced approaches that have been successfully tested abroad These include increasing the accessibility of the capital market for all categories of investors by applying [1]. Currently, a number of practical measures are being taken in order to ensure the implementation of the program and to attract investors through the development of the stock market of our country. At the same time, increasing

the competitiveness of the capital market due to the introduction of attractive mechanisms for investors and increasing its capitalization to 45 trillion sums by the end of 2023 is also determined to improve the capital market and thereby increase the weight of investments [1]. In addition, the Decree No. PD-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [5] provides financial resources in the economy to increase the turnover of the stock market of Uzbekistan from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars by 2027, a huge but effective task has been set. Such attention to the development of the capital market and all the measures taken to improve it play an important role in attracting foreign investments. As a result of the measures aimed at improving and reforming the stock market in our country, as well as the investment environment created in our country and the tax, duty and other state fee concessions provided to attract foreign investors, most of the capital investments in our country are made at the expense of foreign investments. fainting (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Growth rate of fixed capital investments in 2017-2023 (in %) [6]

In 2017, almost a quarter of the total investments were foreign investments, and by 2022, this figure will be 42.8%. 97.0 trillion in 2022 due to direct foreign investments and loans to the economy of our country. Sums of investments in fixed capital were absorbed, their share in the total investments in the Republic was 36.0%, and compared to 2021, it was 104.3% [6]. The stock market is the main indicator of the economy and strengthens the relationship between manufacturing enterprises, service enterprises, commercial banks, stock exchanges, investment institutions and the population [7]. As a result of our research and studies, we can say that the investment potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing year by year, the investment environment is improving year by year, and as a result of the measures implemented to improve the

country's stock market, it is becoming more and more attractive for investment. Taking into account the role of the existing capital market in the volume of attracted investments and, at the same time, the high degree of influence of the level of transparency and openness of the information presented in it on the investor's decision, the fundamental improvement of the existing securities market in our country, its compliance with world standards, ensuring the transparency of the information and the ease of use and modernity of the platform will lead to the improvement of the stock market in our country, which will significantly increase the volume of investments attracted to our country.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2021 No. PD-6207 "On measures to further develop the capital market".
2. Bocharov V.V. Investitsii: Uchebnik - 2 - p. izdaniy - SPb: "Peter" 2009. -348
3. Kristina Levišauskait. Investment Analysis and Portfolio Management. Vytautas Magnus University – 2010. –P.116.
4. S. Elmirzayev. An Analysis of Dividend Policy in Developed Countries and Dividend Aristocrats. "International Finance and Accounting" scientific-electronic magazine, No. 2, 2020. - B.11.
5. Decree No. PD-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
6. Prepared by the author based on information from the official website of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - www.stat.uz
7. Javlon Butaev Inatilloevich. The role and analysis of the stock market in attracting investments. 10th - International Conference on Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education, 2023. -P.4.

